

AN ASSESSMENT OF THE FACTORS THAT INFLUENCES TOURIST VISITATION TO CULTURAL SITES IN NORTHERN ZIMBABWE

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Abstract: Culture motivated trips are on the increase since 1992. As a result, many tourism destinations are using cultural and heritage resources as drivers for destination attractiveness and competitiveness. The creation of culturally distinctive destinations has become an important strategy for tourism destinations in increasingly competitive global tourism markets. It is clear that, a deep understanding of the cultural tourism market, its profile, motivations and behaviours is critical. The objective of this study is to present exploratory results of a study that was carried out to assess the factors that influence tourist visitation to cultural attractions in Northern Zimbabwe. The research was conducted in the Northern part of Zimbabwe as delimited by the National Museums and Monuments of Zimbabwe. Survey data were collected using a self-administered questionnaire. Data were analysed by means of descriptive analysis, factor analyses and multiple regression analyses. Factor analyses produced a 3-factor structure, and therefore, three factors were identified as important influences for visitation. Tourists visits Northern Zimbabwe primarily for personal motivations, relaxation and memorable experiences. The dominant type of tourist was found to be the sightseeing tourist. Multiple regression analyses were applied to predict the most influential visitation factors among cultural tourists. Results are crucial in enhancing understanding of cultural tourism market. This understanding is important for destination managers in Zimbabwe to develop differentiated marketing strategies aimed at increasing arrivals, satisfaction and tourism income.

Keywords: Cultural Tourism, Northern Zimbabwe, Visitation, Multiple Regressions

Introduction

Cultural tourism represents one of the major future growth activities of global tourism (De Simone, 2012; Nyaupane & Andereck, 2014), accounting for more than 40% of the international arrivals (Richards, 2007; OECD, 2009). It is increasingly becoming an important sector for many tourism destinations globally (Kastenholz *et al.*, 2013). OECD (2009) projects further growth of the cultural tourism sector. For instance, roughly 50% of tourism activity in Europe is motivated by culture. In the US, two thirds of adult tourists visits cultural tourism attractions (Richard & Wilson, 2006). Therefore, the demand for cultural tourism is real.

Culture is a pervasive though an extremely important component of tourism (Weaver, Kwek & Wang, 2017). In this regard, Correia, Kozak and Ferradeira (2013) argue, that culture is a significant motivation factor that influences destination choice. Despite the significance of culture as a motivation factor, tourist's behaviour and motivations in a

cultural tourism destination context has not been sufficiently explored (Kastenholz *et al.*, 2013), more so in the context of Zimbabwe. In the tourism context of Zimbabwe, research studies have only focused on the readiness of Zimbabwe to venture into the cultural tourism market (Manwa, 2007), leaving travel behaviour and motivation of cultural tourists not widely explored.

Travel motivation is an essential element that marketers in tourism destinations use to predict the behaviour of visitors (Ngamsom & Beck, 2000). Tourists make travel decisions based on push and pull factors/motivations (Correia & Pimpao, 2008; Crompton, 1979). Culture is a crucial tourist motivation element that is used by tourists in choosing tourism destinations (Correia *et al.* 2013). While the importance of developing cultural tourism has been documented in literature (Richards, 2010; Manwa, 2007), there is a notable lack of academic attention with regards to the investigation of the major characteristics of cultural tourists (Chiang, Wang, Lee & Chen, 2015), particularly in emerging tourism destinations. There is a considerable lack of research that examines the tourists' motivations for cultural tourism from a Zimbabwean perspective.

Considering this gap, the attempt to explore the factors that influence visitation in the context of Northern Zimbabwe is timely and worthy. It is therefore expected that the findings of this study are crucial in helping Zimbabwe to develop strategies that are aimed at enhancing the visitors' cultural experiences. The results could also be important for destination managers to segment the cultural tourism market according to the dominant types of tourists. The motivations of why tourists visit cultural attractions in Northern Zimbabwe is important for tourism managers and marketers as this will influence the destination's branding and marketing materials. Additionally, understanding the type and behaviour of tourists is crucial for Zimbabwe to manage the cultural attractions in a way that is sustainable (Nguyen & Cheung, 2014; Juvan & Dolnicar, 2016) given that, tourism by nature, can affect local culture (Abuamoud, Libbin, Green & Alrousan, 2014).

The purpose of this paper is to assess the motivations of tourists visiting Northern Zimbabwe as a cultural destination. The research questions for this study are:

1. What are the types of cultural tourists that visit Northern Zimbabwe?
2. What are the key motivations that influence cultural tourists to visit Northern Zimbabwe?
3. What effective marketing strategies are there to develop this niche market further help Zimbabwe diversify its tourist base?

Literature Review

Cultural tourism

Ivanovic (2008), argues that, "culture" is a word that was derived from Latin word "cultura" meaning "cultivation". Tomlinson (1991) notes that, there are more than a hundred definitions on culture, yet there is no unanimity on what constitutes culture in literature. Culture is defined as the whole complex of distinctive spiritual, material, intellectual and emotional features that characterises a society or a social group

(UNESCO, 1999). This definition of culture includes creative expressions such as oral history, language, literature, performing arts, fine arts and crafts; additionally, culture also includes the community's practices (for instance traditional healing, traditional natural resources management, celebrations and patterns of social interactions that usually contribute to group welfare and identity; materials and historic buildings such as cultural sites, buildings, historic city centres, landscape, arts and objects (UNESCO, 1999). Research shows that, the UNESCO definition is the only comprehensive definition that can be used appropriately to contextualise cultural tourism (Ivanovic, 2008).

Silberberg (1995:361) defines cultural tourism as “visits by persons from outside the host community motivated wholly or in part by interest in the historical, scientific or lifestyle/heritage offerings of a community, region or institution”. Additionally, cultural tourism includes “activities with cultural content as part of trips and visits with a combination of pursuits” (Medlik, 2003:48). Therefore, the concept of cultural tourism has many synonyms such as heritage tourism, arts tourism and ethnic tourism. Cultural tourism has various elements of learning that enables tourists to have a memorable experience of destination residents' way of life (Richards, 2005, 2010). The debate about the synonyms that are used interchangeably with cultural tourism is beyond the scope of this paper.

Prentice (1993) defines cultural tourism as tourism constructed, proffered and consumed explicitly or implicitly as cultural appreciation, either as experiences or schematic knowledge gaining. Cary (2004:61) notes that, cultural tourism includes experiences and interpretations of specific local cultures such as food, customs, history or product. Wall and Mathieson (2006:261) defines cultural tourism as “tourism that involves experiencing and having contact with a host population and its cultural expressions, experiencing the uniqueness of culture, heritage and the characters of its place and people”. According to Boyd (2002:221), these cultural touristic experiences must ensure “authenticity, quality and the provision of a learning environment by means of interaction and involvement, conserving and protecting resources as well as building partnerships”. Experiences and interpretations of cultural tourism have the potential to induce expressive based reactions. Weaver *et al.*, (2017) argue that, cultural tourism research requires a geographic context to determine the nature of destinations that are being examined and the frameworks that dominate those locations. Therefore, the assessment was done using northern Zimbabwe to provide such geographic context.

It is clear that cultural tourism is a complex term based on the way it has been defined by scholars. There is no agreement about what constitutes cultural tourism, rendering the term to be widely misunderstood (Richards, 2008). The challenge in defining cultural tourism stems from its “wide scope” and the variety of meanings that are ascribed to “culture” (Kastenholz, Eusebio & Carneiro, 2013). More research is required for better conceptualisations of the concept as it will help tourism managers in measuring and marketing cultural tourism (Kastenholz, *et al.*, 2013:345; Mohamed, 2008; Richards, 2005). A technical definition is therefore needed together with a standardised measuring instrument of the cultural tourist motivations. However, in this study, we adopted a technical definition by Richards (1996:24). Richards (1996:24)

defines cultural tourism as “all movements of persons to specific cultural attractions, such as heritage sites, artistic and cultural manifestations, arts and drama outside their normal place of residence.

Impacts of cultural tourism

The benefits that tourism destinations derive from the development of a cultural tourism market are many. Cultural tourism is an important element that can be used to diversify the tourism industry, thus helping destinations to deal with the problem of seasonality (Rudan, 2010). Rudan (2010) argues, cultural tourism helps tourism destinations to improve their images and competitive advantage. The image of a destination is a crucial factor that tourists consider when choosing which destination to holiday (Richards, 2002; Ritchie & Crouch, 2003). Goulding and Domic (2009) argue that, cultural tourism is therefore used as an effective destination branding tool that enhance national pride, destination profile and attracting investments. This particularly, will work for Zimbabwe, as it seeks to reposition itself as a new branded destination with the tagline *Zimbabwe: A World of Wonders* (Ndlovu & Heath, 2013). It will also help Zimbabwe to enhance its destination competitiveness (Kastenholz *et al.*, 2013). It is clear therefore that, the development and promotion of cultural tourism goes beyond economic reasons for many tourism destinations. With Zimbabwe struggling to attract more tourists as a result of its tattered image, the knowledge of travellers’ motivations is crucial for destination marketing messages. The understanding of the travellers’ motivations will also help Zimbabwe to meet the needs of tourists.

Cultural tourism has been gaining importance recently, not only because of economic gains attributable to it (Kastenholz *et al.*, 2013; Abuamoud, *et al.*, 2014). The average daily spending per visitor of a cultural tourist site is 22% higher than that of other visitors (Taylor *et al.*, 1993). A similar study that was conducted in Portugal corroborated that culturally tourists do spend relatively more as compared with other tourist groups (Eusebio *et al.*, 2005). Existing studies on Zimbabwe on cultural tourism has only focused on the country’s readiness in venturing into the cultural tourism market (Manwa, 2007). Therefore, a notable research gap in terms of cultural tourism in Zimbabwe exist. Economic contribution of cultural tourism in Zimbabwe is also yet to be established. This paper contributes towards cultural tourism literature in Zimbabwe by outlining motivations of the tourists visiting Northern Zimbabwe. These motivations are crucial in determining sustainable cultural tourism segments that Zimbabwe and other similar tourism destinations can pursue.

Cultural tourism is a panacea to destinations that are undergoing crises (Viviers & Slabbert, 2012). It helps its local communities in terms of economic development gains (Viviers & Slabbert, 2012; Mazimhaka, 2007; Lee & Han, 2002). As a result, the attention of economists is also recorded in literature (Laplante *et al.*, 2005). There is no doubt that, cultural tourism is a tool of economic development. Tourism destinations, apart from economic development, it can also be used to attract tourism numbers from outside the community, who are motivated wholly or in part by interest in the historical artistic, scientific or lifestyle/heritage offerings of the community, or region (Silberberg, 1995).

Job creation is another tangible impact of cultural tourism. Other impacts of cultural tourism include an increase in tax revenues and quality of life. It is therefore a major source of revenue for many communities and destinations in the world (UNWTO, 2007). Additionally, developing countries have managed to increase their participation in the global economy through the development of cultural tourism (UNWTO, 2007; Richards, 2000, 2009; Richards & Wilson, 2006; Mohamed, 2008). Hence the need to build tourism around a variety of tourist attractions such as agri-tourism, arts tourism, festival tourism, cultural and heritage tourism, destination tourism, fairs, carnivals, events and conferences, sports tourism, and recreation. UNWTO (2007) notes that, the global tourism industry is the largest export earner contributing significantly towards the balance of payments in many countries.

In recent years, particularly at the dawn of the millennium, Zimbabwe's tourism industry has been experiencing problems of poor performance and a decrease in the number of international tourist arrivals (ZTA, 2011; Ndlovu & Heath, 2013; Woyo & Woyo, 2016). More publicity has been given to nature-based tourism focusing on the country's "Big Five Attractions and the Victoria Falls" at the expense of cultural tourist attractions (Manwa, 2007). Cultural tourism research in Zimbabwe is very limited despite the fact that, Zimbabwe has unique cultural attractions. Hence, there is need for research to advise policy makers with regards to the state and potential of cultural tourism in Zimbabwe.

Destinations where tourism is considered an important component of the country's economic base, policy makers find it crucial to expand the potential visitor pool by means of developing and promoting activities that have the ability to appeal to previously untapped segments of the tourism market (McHone & Rungeling, 1999; Sdrahi & Chazapi, 2007). Zimbabwe has long relied solely on wildlife as its main tourist attraction (Manwa, 2007), therefore, it is clear that, cultural tourism is an untapped market. The integration of cultural tourism into the wider national tourism strategy is acknowledged in literature (Poon, 1993; Ritchie, 2003; Dolnicar, 2002; Kim *et al.*, 2007, McKercher, 2002). An improved comprehension of the cultural tourism market in Zimbabwe is therefore important for destination planning, management, designing and promotion of a more satisfying cultural tourism product in a way that is cost effective. Notwithstanding an increased academic interest in the cultural tourist market, little is known about the factors that influences tourist visitation to cultural attractions in Northern Zimbabwe. Knowing these factors could influence the marketing and promotion of cultural tourism. It could also help the destination to leverage the benefits that comes with the development of the cultural tourism market.

Visitor behaviour of cultural tourists

Richards (2007) argues that, cultural motivated trips are on the increase since 1992. The creation of culturally distinctive destinations is therefore an important strategy for tourism destinations, particularly in an increasingly competitive market (OECD, 2009). The creation of distinguishing cultural destinations, however calls for a deep understanding of the cultural tourist market, its profile, motivations, behaviours and heterogeneity (Kastenholz *et al.*, 2013). It is against this background, that tourism destinations like Zimbabwe for example, must view its cultural resources as drivers of destination attractiveness and competitiveness.

Education is recognised as a strong determinant of cultural tourism visitation than income levels (Kim *et al.*, 2007; Richards, 2000; Kastenholtz *et al.*, 2013). According to Kim *et al.*, (2007), on one hand, cultural tourists with a higher level of education and income participates more in cultural attractions such as local festival, fairs, musical attractions and knowledge/aesthetic seeking attractions. On the other hand, low income cultural tourists were found to prefer participating in commercial recreation parks, suggesting a low interest and knowledge about the local culture (Kim *et al.*, 2007; Kerstetter, Confer & Graefe, 2001). Additionally, cultural tourists have enough leisure time to explore and experience cultural tourism (Richards, 2007).

Socio-economic status of visitors is an effective predictor for cultural tourist visitation in the United States (Kim, *et al.*, 2007). This finding was corroborated by Richards (2007). The behaviour of cultural tourists is influenced by a number of factors that shapes tourists' motivation to travel and choose destination. Destination image and other evaluative factors like trip quality, observed value and satisfaction stimulates visitors' behaviour directly (Prayag, 2010). Research shows that, destination image is a critical element that influences choice. Image has a profound effect with regards to the tourists' behavioural intentions particularly the intention to revisit and willingness to make recommendations about a destination (Chen & Tsai, 2007; Prayag, 2010). While the tourist's motivations and behaviours have been explored in other cultural tourism destinations, similar research is yet to establish the key motivations of cultural tourists in the empirical context of Zimbabwe as a cultural tourism destination.

Typologies of cultural tourists

There is a growing stream of literature that explored the typologies of cultural and heritage tourists (*see*, Kerstetter, Confer, & Graefe, 2001; McKercher, 2002; McKercher & du Cros, 2003; McKercher, Ho, du Cros, & So-Ming, 2002; Nyaupane, White, & Budmk, 2006; Silberberg, 1995). Five types of cultural heritage tourists were proposed by McKercher (2002) based on the level of importance they put on cultural tourism by means of analysing the way tourists make decisions and the experience they are seeking. The types according to McKercher (2002) include: incidental cultural tourists, casual cultural tourists, sightseeing cultural tourists, serendipitous cultural tourists and purposeful cultural tourists. These typologies were empirically tested by McKercher and du Cross (2003). However, these typologies are yet to be empirically investigated in the context of Zimbabwe as a tourism destination. Therefore, profiling of cultural tourists in Zimbabwe is therefore critical.

Another study on typologies of cultural tourists was done by Nyaupane *et al.*, (2006). In their study, they identified three types of tourists, which they labelled based on the motives of tourists to learn about the destination's cultural history (Nyaupane & Andereck, 2014). The identified types were culture focused, culture attentive and culture appreciative. According to Nyaupane *et al.*, (2006) there is a continuum that can be identified in empirical studies in relation to cultural tourists. However, studies that have empirical analysed the typologies of cultural tourists based on their behaviour (that is visiting certain attractions) are relatively few (de Simone, 2012). These typologies have not been empirically tested in Zimbabwe, and there is a typological research gap that requires further research.

Other scholars categorised the types of cultural tourists based on visitors' experience they are seeking in a tourism destination (e.g. Hudson, 2009). According to Hudson (2009), cultural tourists can therefore be classified based on behaviours that are constructed using their travel experiences and motivations for holiday-taking. The categories of cultural tourists that Hudson (2009) developed include: bubble travellers, idealised-experience seekers, wide horizon travellers and total immersers. Johns and Gyimothy (2002) classified cultural tourist behaviours into two major categories, and they labelled the tourists as active vacationers and inactive vacationers. Active vacationers are cultural tourists who seek local culture and value the destination's amenities while active vacationers are tourists who only visit popular cultural attractions (Johns & Gyimothy, 2002). Both typologies have not been empirically investigated in the context of Northern Zimbabwe as a cultural tourism destination.

Visitor experiences constitute a major component of cultural tourism marketing. Research shows that, a growing number of cultural tourists are seeking a total visitation experience that is not limited to learning but also involves culture, leisure and social interaction. These elements of vacation are associated with a memorable tourist experience (Kim, Ritchie & McCormick, 2010). The destination's attributes play a much bigger role in influencing satisfaction and ultimately the cultural tourism experience (Huh *et al.*, 2006). Tourists are believed to recall easily the positive aspects of their travel experience than the negative aspects, indicating the need for destination managers in Zimbabwe to provide more memorable travel experiences for cultural tourists. This can be achieved by formulating interesting cultural programmes that can help tourists visiting Zimbabwe to experience and discover new things (Kim *et al.*, 2010). It is clear that research has been conducted on travel behaviour and motivations; however limited attention has been shown in the context of Zimbabwean tourism. Therefore, the contribution of this paper is in its context.

Tourist motivation of cultural tourists

There is no doubt that cultural/heritage tourism is a fast-growing segment of the wider tourism market (Correia *et al.*, 2013). This trend is evident based on the increase of the volume of tourists that are seeking adventure, culture, history, archaeology and interaction with the local people within tourism destinations (Hughes & Allen, 2005; Nuryanti, 1996). The cultural tourism market is a favourable option for many tourism destinations because of the higher spending behaviour of the cultural tourists (Correia *et al.*, 2013). Therefore, understanding the motivations of such a market is critical for destination managers in Zimbabwe.

Research suggests that motivation referring consumption experience plays a significant role in customer retention and customer loyalty (Mathwick, Malhotra & Rigdon, 2002). Based on this, it is important for marketers to be familiarised with their customers, particularly in terms of their behaviour and motivations by focusing on why they purchase, how many repeat purchasers exist and how often have they purchase goods and services (Oppermann, 1999). Therefore, in a cultural tourism context, a better comprehension of why tourists travel and visit cultural attractions is important for successful destination marketing (Crompton, & McKay, 1997; Prentice & Andersen, 2003; Song, You, Reisinger, Lee & Lee, 2014) and visitor management. It is suggested

that, the characteristics of the tourists is influential in attracting potential visitors to tourism destinations (Richards, 2002).

The behavioural intention of visitors is directly influenced by the desires of tourists to attend cultural events (Song *et al.*, 2014), suggesting that, the visitors' positive anticipation emotion is key in generating the need to explore local cultural activities and identities (Chiang *et al.*, 2015). Cultural events and attractions are other motivators that influences tourists to visit a tourism destination (Chang, 2006; Correia *et al.*, 2013). Based on this, it is important for tourism managers in Zimbabwe to understand the key characteristics and motivations for cultural tourists so that, the major markets could be classified and the demand for cultural tourism be understood (Rid, Ezeuduji & Pröbstl-Haider, 2014). In the context of the Gambia, tourists visit cultural attractions for the purposes of seeking heritage and nature based activities, multi-experience based activities; beach based activities; sun and beach based activities (Rid, Ezeuduji & Pröbstl-Haider, 2014). The motivations of cultural tourists in Zimbabwe remains unknown. The understanding of travel motivations of cultural tourists is therefore, a precursor for destinations to be successful in their planning (Severt, Wang, Chen & Breiter, 2007) and visitor management. With a growing stream of interest in cultural tourism, particularly segmentation and satisfaction, there is limited and/or no research that has explored the factors that influences tourist to visit Northern Zimbabwe as a cultural tourism destination.

Method of Research

Sample and data collection

This study seeks to identify the types and motivations of cultural tourists that visit Northern Zimbabwe as a cultural tourism destination. A survey instrument was developed to identify the types of tourists and factors that influences tourists to visit cultural sites. The study was conducted between October 2013 and February 2014. Primary data were collected through a survey questionnaire that was administered by the researchers at 6 different sites in Northern Zimbabwe: Zimbabwe Museum of Human Sciences, Chiremba Balancing Rocks, Ngomakurira National Monument, Tsindi Ruins, Domboshava National Monument, and Mutoko Ruins (*see* Fig. 1 for the delimitation of the study area). The survey instrument that was used in this study was developed to address the study objectives and to answer the research question. A large sample $N= 500$ was selected from international tourists to participate in this study.

Survey participants were asked to indicate their demographic characteristics such as gender, age and education. The study also investigated the typology of cultural tourists. The last section of the survey instrument asked tourists about the factors that influenced their visitation to cultural sites and an option for suggesting and commenting about their visit was also provided in instrument. Face and content validity of the research's preliminary questionnaire was assessed through a focus group discussion that involved a panel of tourism experts who were drawn from the higher education institutions in Zimbabwe. A focus group discussion was done with 5 postgraduate students majoring in Cultural Tourism Management. The motive behind the focus group discussions was to establish and ascertain the most probable reasons that motivate tourists to visit cultural attractions. As a result, each participant within

the focus group discussion was able to comprehensively assess the importance of including the questions in the survey. A panel of Tourism Management experts were later involved in the reviewing of the revised questionnaire. These experts included university professors and doctoral degree holders. Experts were asked to make comments with regards to the representativeness, clarity, the testing format, wording and particularly the item content of the questionnaire. Based on the comments and feedback received from the panel of tourism experts, the research questionnaire was therefore modified and administered to tourists by the researchers.

Figure 1: Map of study area

Data analysis

The study's data analysis followed three steps: first, descriptive analysis was performed and focused on the profile and typologies of the respondents. The second step of data analysis focused on factor analyses. Factor analyses were conducted using the principal component analysis (PCA). The motivation in conducting the PCA was to identify factors that reflected a larger set of the visitation motivation items that were included in the questionnaire. The last step of data analysis focused on regression analyses and it focused on analysing significant motivation factors in the context of Northern Zimbabwe.

Results and Discussion

Summary of the visitor profile

The response rate was 86%, as 430 of the 500 questionnaires were returned to the researchers with usable responses. In terms of gender composition, the study recorded more female visitors (69.8%) as compared to male visitors (30.2%) as shown in Table 1. The majority of the respondents were married (56.3%) and were found to be educated up to the Bachelors' degree level. The level of education was found to be high, corroborating the findings of research done by McKercher (2002) and Richards (2001). Therefore, for Zimbabwe to develop its cultural tourism market, they need to target more of the educated tourists because they are able to comprehend and understand the product offering better. The average age of the visitors to cultural attractions in Northern Zimbabwe was 30 years. This is contrary to the findings of Richards (2001) who argued that, the cultural tourism market attracts older travellers. In terms of source markets, 83.72% of the respondents were from the African continent and this is attributable to proximity; Europe 5.81%; Asia Pacific recorded 5.35% while tourists from Europe and the Expanded Middle East were 2.79% and 2.33% respectively. Therefore, it is important for destination managers to develop and market the cultural tourism product for the short haul market.

Table 1: Description statistics of the sample

Variable	<i>N=430</i>	%
Gender		
Male	130	30.2
Female	300	69.8
Age in years		
24 -30	100	23.3
31 – 35	150	34.9
36 -40	90	20.9
41 -50	40	9.3
51 -60	30	7.0
≥61	20	4.7
Marital Status		
Married	242	56.3
Single	150	34.9
Widow	38	8.8
Education Level		
Secondary Education	30	7.0
National Certificate	10	2.3
National Diploma	30	7.0
Higher national Diploma	10	2.3
Bachelor's degree	250	58.1
Graduate School	100	23.3
Source Markets		
Africa	360	83.7
Europe	25	5.8
Asia Pacific	23	5.4
Americas	12	2.8
Expanded Middle East	10	2.3

Cultural tourist typologies

It was also the objective of this study to identify the types of cultural tourists that visit Northern Zimbabwe as a cultural tourism destination. The most dominant type of cultural tourists is the sightseeing cultural tourists (40% of the sample) as shown in Table 2. This was followed by the casual and purposeful tourists (20% respectively). Serendipitous cultural tourists accounted for 17.4% of the sample while the incidental tourists were 2.6% of the sample. The findings of this study are helpful in helping destination managers in segmenting the cultural tourism market. Additionally, this information is crucial for cultural destination managers to understand the different types of needs that tourists have and could be helpful in the design and development of facilities.

Cultural tourist typologies in Northern Zimbabwe

Tourist typology	Frequency	%
Sightseeing cultural tourist	172	40%
Casual cultural tourist	86	20%
Purposeful cultural tourist	86	20%
Serendipitous cultural tourist	75	17.4%
Incidental cultural tourist	11	2.6%

The findings of this study are therefore in tandem with previous studies. Niemczyk (2013) conducted a survey whose findings indicated that, travel motivations for participation in cultural tourism are based on multiple-dimensions such as purposeful, serendipitous, sightseeing, incidental and casual dimensions.

Cultural tourist motivations

The other objective of the study was to identify the major motivations of tourists in the context of Northern Zimbabwe as a cultural tourism destination. The motivations were factor analysed using an Oblimin oblique rotation that followed the principal component analysis (PCA) of the factors. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) generated cultural tourists' behavioural dimensions with a three-factor structure. These factors had eigenvalues that were greater than 1 (Zikmund *et al.*, 2010:594). The total variance for the three factors was explained by 66.01% of the variances. The study deemed this to be satisfactory as per the guidelines of Hair *et al.*, (2013). The Bartlett's test of sphericity after running the analysis was a *p-value* that was lower than 0.001 ($p < 0.000$) indicating statistical significance (Malhorta *et al.*, 2013:364). Therefore, cultural tourists' visitation motivation for factor analyses were supported.

The rotation converged in 8 iterations and the Kaiser-Meyer Olkin measure of sampling adequacy for the factors was 0.814. The KMO was deemed to be appropriate as high values are considered between 0.5 and 1 (Malhorta *et al.*, 2013:624). The majority of the items that were loaded for factor analysis had higher than 0.3 factor loadings and this showed that there was correlation between the variables and the factors (Malhorta *et al.*, 2013:624). The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was used in this study to assess the internal consistency among the items that were observed for factor analyses. This was done to confirm if the data that was collected was reliable. The reliability coefficients

ranged from 0.66 to 0.75, thus, exceeding what Malhorta (2010) defined as an acceptable cut off coefficient. Elements that cross loaded in either factor 1, 2 or 3 were classified in the factor in which the researchers felt was more appropriate based on literature.

Table 3: Factor analysis results

Motivational factors	Factor loading	Cronbach's Alpha
Factor 1: Personal motivation		0.75
Specifically wanted to visit the area	0.67	
I am an artist/professional in the industry	0.66	
Visited only because of friends/relatives visited	0.64	
The cultural site was part of the package	0.64	
I am interested in history	0.61	
Something to tell my friends/relatives about	0.55	
Factor 2: Relaxation motivation		
To relax physically	0.77	
To relax spiritually	0.68	
Just wanted something to do in culture	0.58	
Interested in the destination's nightlife	0.58	
A break from normal routine	0.55	
Factor 3: Memorable experience seeking		0.67
To make new friends	0.64	
To experience something authentic	0.61	
To experience something new	0.59	
Site provides an educational experience	0.55	

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Oblimin oblique with Kaiser Normalization

Factor 1: Personal motivation

The study found that, the respondents were motivated in visiting Northern Zimbabwe for personal reasons. The factor had a total of 6 factor items. The first factor identified the personal motivation factor and it describes the tourists' motivations to visiting cultural based attractions in Northern Zimbabwe. All the factor items were retained for further analysis as they had factor loadings that were greater than 0.3. A high reliability coefficient of 0.75 indicates that, there is a relatively high internal consistency between the factor items that were loaded for factor analyses. This factor integrates factor items such as "specifically wanted to visit the area", "I am an artist/professional in the industry", "visited only because of friends/relatives visited", "the cultural site was part of the package" and "I am interested in history". The development of cultural tourism facilities in Northern Zimbabwe must focus on personal motivation factors. There is

need for destination managers to develop facilities and cultural activities that attracts artists and researchers for example.

Factor 2: Relaxation

The second factor integrated items such as “to relax spiritually”, “just wanted something to do with culture”, “interested in destination’s night life”, “for resting and relaxation”, and a “break from normal routine”. The factor generated a reliability score of 0.66, suggesting a relatively high internal consistency among the factor items. The marketing of cultural tourism in Northern Zimbabwe must focus its messages on relaxation, given that, tourists mainly visit the destination to relax spiritually and for resting. The development of facilities must also ensure that tourists are able to relax when they visit the destination, hence the need for accommodation facilities. Destination managers must also focus on the development of attractive and authentic destination life as most respondents indicated that it is an important motivation factor.

Factor 3: Seeking memorable experience

This factor identified memorable tourist’s experience as an important motivation factor influencing visitation. The factor described the tourists’ cultural experiences to Northern Zimbabwe’s cultural sites. The factor integrated items such as “to make new friends”, “to experience something new”, “to experience something authentic” and “the site provides an educational experience”. The factor generated a Cronbach’s Alpha value of 0.67, suggesting that there was a relatively high internal consistency among the factor items. This finding validates the views of Kim *et al.*, (2010), who conclude that, holiday makers tend to recollect positive travel experiences, suggesting that, cultural tourism destinations are required to deliver unforgettable travel experiences by means of developing exciting programmes that tourists can experience as they discover new things. McKercher (2002) also notes that, purposeful cultural tourists, on their part, are tourists that seek deep and memorable travel experiences as their main motivation to travel to cultural attractions.

Significant factors influencing cultural tourism visitation

The study used multiple regression analyses to determine significant factors that influences tourists’ visitation to cultural attractions in Northern Zimbabwe. As can be seen in Table 4, only 4 independent variables were found to be significantly influential in with regards to the motivation by tourists wanting to visit cultural attractions. Tourists who are artists/professionals are more likely to visit cultural and archaeological sites ($\beta = .350$). Additionally, the need for tourists to tell their friends and relatives about something is the second most significant influential factor in predicting visitation to cultural sites ($\beta = .242$). Thus, one would expect that, these variables are significant and influential in explaining the factors that influence visitation to cultural attractions sites in Northern Zimbabwe, and therefore justifies the need for the tourism industry to develop and diversity its tourism products given that, its nature based tourism has since been regarded as “tired” (Manwa, 2007).

Table 5 shows that 3 factor items are significant in explaining relaxation as an influencing visitation factor to cultural attractions in Northern Zimbabwe. To relax physically ($\beta = .558$) is a more significant in influencing tourist visitation to cultural sites in Northern Zimbabwe. This was followed by the desire of tourists in wanting

something to do with culture ($\beta = .242$). Table 6 also shows that, there are only two significant factors that can explain cultural tourist visitation in terms of the experience seeking tourists. The need for tourists to experience something new is more significant in explaining tourist visitation in the context of experience seeking factor ($\beta = .236$).

Table 4: Multiple regression model for factor I (personal motivation)

Model fit	R = .634; R ² = .403; f = 57.138; α = 0.000				
Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
(Constant)	-0.218	0.285		-0.767	0.444
I am an artist/professional in industry	0.424	0.053	0.35	8.065	.000*
Visited only because friends/relatives visited	0.264	0.084	0.17	3.154	.002*
Cultural site was part of the tour package	0	0.074	0	-0.002	0.999
Something to tell my friends/relatives about	0.21	0.035	0.242	5.938	.000*
Interested in the destination's nightlife	0.131	0.04	0.135	3.26	.001*

Statistically significant at 95% level ($p < 0.05$)

Table 5: Multiple regression model for factor II (relaxation)

Model fit	R = .740; R ² = .547; f = 128.388; α = 0.000				
Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	0.025	0.297		0.084	0.933
A break from normal routine	-0.02	0.062	-0.012	-0.328	0.743
Just wanted something to do in culture	0.232	0.038	0.242	6.164	.000*
To relax physically	0.573	0.041	0.558	13.899	.000*
Interested in the destination's nightlife	0.156	0.056	0.1	2.783	.006*

Statistically significant at 95% level ($p < 0.05$)

Table 6: Multiple regression model for factor III (experience seeking tourist)

Model fit		R = .305; R ² = .093; f = 14.559; α = 0.000			
Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	2.322	0.262		8.878	0.00
To make new friends	0.188	0.056	0.169	3.332	.001*
Site provide an educational experience	-0.061	0.067	-0.055	-0.951	0.361
To experience something new	0.242	0.061	0.236	3.959	.000*

Statistically significant at 95% level (p < 0.05)

R-squared is a statistical measure of how close the data are to the fitted regression line, and it is also known as a coefficient of determination. In the context of multiple regression analyses that were conducted in this study, it ranged from 0.093 to 0.547. Factor III generated a low r-squared value of 0.093 and there are many possible explanations for such a low value. One of the reasons why the regression analyses of factor III resulted in a low value is that, the explanatory variables that were regressed might not have been good enough (Pindiyeck & Rubinfeld, 1981). This might suggest that, there are more important factors that can help explain the experience seeking motivation of tourists in Zimbabwe. However, it is important to note that, the low values of r-squared do not threaten the scientific contribution of the study since the purpose of this study was to identify the factors that influences visitation than fitting the data to a defined model.

Managerial Implications and Suggestions

This study revealed that tourists visiting Northern Zimbabwe can be clustered into five major categories “sightseeing”, “casual”, “purposeful”, “serendipitous” and “incidental” cultural visitors. These categories can be used in Zimbabwe as the basis of segmenting the cultural tourism market. Sightseeing tourists were found in this study to be the largest group of cultural tourists visiting Zimbabwe. Therefore, sightseeing is the primary motivation for visiting Northern Zimbabwe as a cultural destination. Therefore, in targeting visitors for the purposes of sightseeing, destination managers in Northern Zimbabwe may need to consider destination marketing messages that focuses on key attractions in the region. Campaigns can be conducted on virtual spaces such as YouTube and other social media spaces like Facebook and Twitter to recommend potential tourists to visit and take part in novel tourism activities at cultural based attractions in Northern Zimbabwe. Additionally, destination marketing messages must also focus on attracting visitors seeking relaxation and memorable experiences as they are more environmentally conscious.

After Manwa (2007)’s study on the readiness of Zimbabwe in venturing into cultural tourism market, the comprehension of factors influencing visitation of tourists in the

context of cultural tourism was considered important. The study identified three important factors that motivate tourists to visit Northern Zimbabwe as a cultural tourism destination. These factors are “personal motivation”, “relaxation” and “seeking memorable experience”. It is therefore suggested that, tourism managers and policy makers in Zimbabwe must improve cultural facilities for increased visitation by artists and professionals to cultural attractions. In addition, there is need for the cultural tourism sector in Northern Zimbabwe to increase opportunities for relaxation and new experience explorations for visitors that are seeking memorable experiences. Based on the findings of the study, the 3-factor structure that was extracted provides a description of the variables that relate to the motivations of why tourists visit cultural attractions in Northern Zimbabwe. These factors are important in providing an understanding of the important factors that influences visitation to Northern Zimbabwe. Such an understanding is crucial in helping cultural and heritage planners with information needed for the development and formulation of effective strategies.

One of the limitations of the study is the subsequent lack of generalisability due to limited nature of the survey to one region and the sample only focused on international travellers at a time when tourism industry was not relatively busy. The study focused only on Northern Region, and other regions must be studied in the future given that, they have different cultural sites, hence the factors influencing visitation might also be different. More investigation must also be conducted to measure the demand of cultural tourism in Zimbabwe and how the market can be further segmented.

In conclusion, these results have important destination planning and marketing implications for Northern Zimbabwe and other regions as cultural tourism destinations. Managers of tourism in these areas can actually use the findings of the study to develop cost-effective marketing strategies for the various types of tourists that were identified as target groups.

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